

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Paper

Forced Degradation Studies of Topiroxostat Tablet by UV-Visible Spectroscopy as Per ICH Guidelines

Krishna Tandel^{*1}, Gayatri Paliwal², Alisha Patel³, Bhavesh Patel⁴

^{1,2,3} Pharmaceutical Quality Assurance, ROFEL Shri G.M. Bilakhia College of Pharmacy, Vapi.

⁴ Department of Chemistry, Shri C. N. F Arts and D. N. Science College, Dabhoi..

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 07 May 2026

Keywords:

Topiroxostat, UV-Visible spectroscopy, Forced degradation, ICH guidelines, Method validation, stress testing

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.20068145

ABSTRACT

Forced degradation studies of Topiroxostat tablets were carried out using a validated UV-Visible spectrophotometric method as per ICH guidelines. The method was developed using methanol as solvent, with maximum absorbance observed at 275 nm. The calibration curve showed good linearity within the concentration range of 6-14 µg/ml with a correlation coefficient of 0.9977. Validation studies performed in accordance with ICH Q2 (R2) guidelines confirmed that accuracy, precision, linearity, limit of detection (LOD), and limit of quantitation (LOQ) were found to be within acceptable limits. Forced degradation studies were performed under various stress conditions including acidic, basic, neutral hydrolysis, oxidative, thermal, and photolytic environment. The drug showed varying degrees of degradation under these conditions, indicating its susceptibility to stress factors. The developed method is simple, rapid, and reliable for routine analysis and stability assessment of Topiroxostat in pharmaceutical dosage forms. These studies help in understanding degradation pathways and ensure drug quality, safety, and efficacy. The developed method is well-suited for routine quality control, content uniformity testing, and preliminary stability studies of Topiroxostat in pharmaceutical formulations

INTRODUCTION

Gout is a chronic inflammatory disease characterized by the deposition of monosodium urate crystals in joints and tissues, resulting from

rolonged hyperuricemia, leading to severe joint pain and inflammation [1].

Topiroxostat is a selective Xanthine Oxidase inhibitor used to treat and control gout and hyperuricemia. Purine metabolism is regulated by xanthine oxidase, also known as xanthine

***Corresponding Author:** Krishna Tandel

Address: ROFEL Shri G. M. Bilakhia College of Pharmacy, Namdha Campus, Vapi-Namdha Road, Vapi (West) - 396191, District Valsad, Gujarat, India

Email ✉: krishatandel1806@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

oxidoreductase (XOR), and serum urate levels can be effectively decreased by inhibiting the enzyme. 4-(5-pyridine-4-yl-1H-1, 2, 4-triazol-3-yl)pyridine-2-Carbonitrile is the IUPAC name of Topiroxostat and 248.24 g/mol [2, 3].

Figure. 1 Structure of Topiroxostat

Stability-indicating methods are quantitative analytical techniques that utilize the unique structural, chemical, or biological properties of each active ingredient in a drug product. These methods enable the differentiation between the active ingredient and its degradation products, allowing for accurate measurement of the active content [4].

The ICH guideline Q1A on “Stability Testing of New Drug Substances and Products” gives indications for the testing parameters which are

may be susceptible to change during long storage and are likely to affect quality, safety and efficacy must be done by validated stability indicating testing methods. It is mentioned that forced degradation studies or stress testing at temperatures in 10°C increments above the accelerated temperatures, and under acidic, basic, neutral hydrolysis, oxidative, and photolytic conditions have to be carried out on the drug substance so to set up the stability characteristics and degradation pathways to back up the suitability of the proposed analytical procedures [5]. Instruments which measure the ratio, or a function of the ratio, of the intensity of two beams of light in the ultraviolet region are called UV-Visible Spectrophotometers. The technique of UV-Visible Spectrophotometry is one of the most frequently employed in Pharmaceutical Analysis. It involves the measurement of the amount of Ultraviolet (200-400nm) or visible (400-800nm) radiation absorbed by substance in solution. Absorption of light in both the UV and visible regions of the electromagnetic spectra occurs when the energy of light matches that required to induced in the molecular electronic transition and its associated vibrational and rotational transitions. It is thus convenient to consider the techniques of UV and visible spectrophotometry together [6, 7].

Figure. 2 UV-Visible Spectrophotometry

The present study aims to develop and validate a UV spectrophotometric method for the estimation of Topiroxostat and to evaluate its degradation behavior under different stress conditions as per ICH guidelines.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Chemical and Reagents: All reagents and solvents employed in this study were of analytical grade. Topiroxostat (bulk drug) and a commercial tablet formulation containing 20 mg of Topiroxostat were obtained from Alkem Laboratories, Alkem House, Mumbai, India. Methanol was procured from Rankem. Hydrochloric acid (HCl), Sodium hydroxide (NaOH), and Hydrogen Peroxide (H₂O₂) were used for forced degradation studies. Distilled water was used throughout the study.

Instruments: UV-Visible spectrophotometric analysis was carried out using a double beam UV-

Visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-1900i) equipped with LabSolutions UV-Vis software and 1 cm pathlength quartz cuvettes. An analytical balance (REPTech) and an ultrasonicator (Themis Medicare) was used.

Preparation of Standard Solution: An accurately weighed quantity of Topiroxostat (20mg) was transferred to a 50 ml volumetric flask, dissolved in methanol with sonication, and volume was made up to the mark to obtain a stock solution of 400 µg/ml. Further dilution of 1.25 ml of this solution to 10 ml with methanol yield a working standard solution of 50 µg/ml.

Determination of Wavelength of Maximum Absorbance (λ_{max}): An aliquot of the working solution was suitably diluted to obtain a concentration of 10 µg/ml and scanned in the range of 200-400nm against methanol as blank. The maximum absorbance (λ_{max}) was observed at 275 nm, which was selected for further analysis [8].

Figure 3. Absorbance Spectra of Topiroxostat (10 µg/ml)

Preparation of Calibration Curve: Standard solution in the concentration range of 6-14 µg/ml were prepared by appropriate dilution of the working standard solution. The absorbance of each solution was measured at 275 nm against methanol as blank. The calibration curve was constructed by plotting absorbance (A) versus Concentration (C, µg/ml).

Method Validation: The objective of method validation is to demonstrate that the method is

suitable for its intended purpose. The method was validated for linearity, precision, accuracy, LOD, and LOQ as per ICH guidelines [9].

- Linearity:** Linearity was determined by analyzing standard solutions in the range of 6-14 µg/ml. Calibration curve of absorbance vs. concentration was plotted and correlation coefficient and regression line equations for Topiroxostat were calculated.

2. **Precision:** The repeatability of the method was checked by scanning 10 µg/ml of solution six times. Intra-day precision was determined by checking absorbance of 8-12 µg/ml on the same day. Inter-day precision was determined by checking the absorbance of 8-12 µg/ml on three different days. The % RSD was calculated.
 3. **Accuracy:** Accuracy study was conducted by spiking at three different concentration levels (80%, 100%, and 120%). At each level samples were scanned and from the absorbance % recovery was determined.
 4. **Limit of Detection (LOD):** LOD is the lowest amount of an analyte in a sample that can be detected, but not necessarily quantified, under stated experimental conditions. Estimated from the set of 5 calibration curves that were used to determine linearity. $LOD = 3.3 \times S.D./Slope$
 5. **Limit of Quantitation (LOQ):** LOQ is the lowest amount of an analyte in a sample that can be quantified under stated experimental conditions. Estimated from the set of 5 calibration curves that were used to determine linearity. $LOQ = 10 \times S.D./Slope$
- For all conditions, Topiroxostat equivalent to 20mg was weighed accurately and exposed to the following environments:
1. **Acidic Degradation:** 20 mg Topiroxostat in 2ml of 0.1N HCl and allowed to rest for 30 minutes. After that sample was neutralized with 2ml of 0.1 N NaOH.
 2. **Basic Degradation:** 20 mg Topiroxostat in 2ml of 0.1 N NaOH and allowed to rest for 30 minutes. After that sample was neutralized with 2ml of 0.1 N HCl.
 3. **Neutral Degradation:** 20 mg Topiroxostat dissolved in 2 ml Distilled water and allowed to rest for 30 minutes.
 4. **Oxidative Degradation:** 20 mg Topiroxostat treated with 2 ml 3% hydrogen peroxide solution and allowed to rest for 30 minutes.
 5. **Photolytic Degradation:** 20 mg Topiroxostat exposed to direct sunlight for 30 minutes [11].
 6. **Thermal Degradation:** 20 mg Topiroxostat placed in hot air oven at 45-50°C for 30 minutes.
- After each stress treatment, samples were diluted with methanol to yield a concentration of 10 µg/ml. The absorbance of each sample was measured at 275 nm, and the percentage of degradation was calculated using the initial absorbance of the unstressed sample.

Assay of Commercial Tablet Formulations:

Tablet powder equivalent to 20 mg of Topiroxostat was accurately weighed, dissolved in methanol, sonicated for 5 minutes, and filtered through Whatmann filter paper. Appropriate dilutions were made to obtain a final concentration of 10 µg/ml, and absorbance was measured at 275 nm to determine drug content.

Forced Degradation Studies: Forced degradation studies were performed to evaluate the stability of Topiroxostat under different stress conditions, following ICH Q1A (R2) guidelines [10].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Linearity and Calibration Curve: The developed method exhibited excellent linearity within the validated concentration range of 6-14 µg/ml. The absorbance values for each concentration was measured at 275 nm and are presented in Table 1. The calibration curve of absorbance vs. concentration showed a straight line with a regression equation: $y = 0.0634x - 0.0231$ with regression coefficient (R^2) 0.9956 and correlation coefficient (r) 0.9977.

Table 1. Linearity of Topiroxostat

Sr. No.	Concentration (µg/ml)	Mean Abs. ± S.D. (n=5)	%RSD
1.	6	0.353 ± 0.004	1.181
2.	8	0.488 ± 0.003	0.775
3.	10	0.624 ± 0.008	1.368
4.	12	0.717 ± 0.003	0.533
5.	14	0.873 ± 0.009	1.103

The absorbance values were below 1.0, ensuring reliable quantitative analysis.

Calibration Curve of Topiroxostat was presented in Figure 4:

Figure. 4 Calibration Curve of Topiroxostat

Precision: The method demonstrated acceptable intraday, and interday studies and are presented in precision with low %RSD values for repeatability, Tables.

Table 2. Repeatability of Topiroxostat

Sr. No.	Drug	Concentration (µg/ml)	Mean Abs. ± S.D. (n=6)	%RSD
1.	Topiroxostat	10	0.621 ± 0.004	0.752

Table 3. Intraday Precision of Topiroxostat

Sr. No.	Concentration (µg/ml)	Mean Abs. ± S.D. (n=3)	%RSD
1.	8	0.486 ± 0.004	1.009
2.	10	0.620 ± 0.007	1.218
3.	12	0.723 ± 0.006	0.829

Table 4. Interday Precision of Topiroxostat

Sr. No.	Concentration (µg/ml)	Mean Abs. ± S.D. (n=3)	%RSD
1.	8	0.490 ± 0.006	1.264
2.	10	0.621 ± 0.008	1.333
3.	12	0.721 ± 0.007	1.007

The %RSD values were found to be within acceptable limits (<2%), confirming the reliability and reproducibility of the method.

Accuracy: Accuracy was evaluated by recovery studies at 80%, 100%, and 120% levels. The

percentage recovery values were found to be within the acceptable range of 98-102%, indicating the method is accurate and free from interference.

Table 5. Accuracy of Topiroxostat

Sr. No.	Level	Amount added (µg/ml)	Amount found (µg/ml)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
1.	0%	6	5.95	99.17	
2.	80%	10.8	10.78	99.89	99.46
3.	100%	12	11.93	99.42	
4.	120%	13.2	13.11	99.34	

LOD and LOQ: The LOD and LOQ for Topiroxostat were found to be 0.55 µg/ml and 1.69 µg/ml.

Assay of Topiroxostat tablets: The developed method was successfully applied to the analysis of

Topiroxostat (20mg) in Tablet dosage form. The assay results were found to be within acceptable limits, confirming the applicability of the method for routine quality control analysis.

Table 6. Assay of Topiroxostat tablets

Sample	Actual Concentration (µg/ml)	Amount obtained Mean ± S.D. (n=3) (µg/ml)	%purity ± S.D. (n=3)
Topiroxostat Tablet (20mg)	10	0.608 ± 0.0006	99.65 ± 0.098

Table 7. Summary of UV- spectroscopic method

Parameters	Value
Wavelength (nm)	275 nm
Linearity (µg/ml)	6-14 µg/ml
Regression equation (y = mx + C)	Y= 0.0634x – 0.0231
Slope (m)	0.0634
Intercept (C)	0.0231
Regression coefficient (R ²)	0.9956
Correlation coefficient ®	0.9977
Repeatability (n=6)	0.752
Intraday precision (n=3) (%RSD)	1.009 – 0.829
Interday Precision (n=3) (%RSD)	1.264 – 1.007
LOD (µg/ml)	0.558
LOQ (µg/ml)	1.691
% Recovery (n=3)	99.17 – 99.34
% Assay (n=3)	99.65

The test result of proposed method found to within acceptable limit.

Forced degradation studies: Forced degradation testing was carried out to evaluate the stability

behavior of Topiroxostat under a variety of stress conditions including acid, base, neutral hydrolysis, oxidative, thermal, and photolytic degradation.

Figure. 5 Control Absorbance (10µg/ml)

Table 8. Control Condition for Topiroxostat

Condition	Time	Absorbance	Concentration	% Potency	% Degradation
Control	0hr	0.608	10	100	-

1. Acid Degradation:

Spectra of acid degradation is shown in figure 6 and Table 9 shows % degradation in acidic conditions.

Figure. 6 Spectra of acid hydrolysis

Table 9. Acid degradation condition

Condition	Time	Absorbance	Conc. Obtained (µg/ml)	% Potency	% Degradation
Control	0 hr	0.608	10	100	-
0.1 N HCl	30 mins	0.478	7.18	71.8	28.10

The degradation in acidic condition was found to be 28.10 %.

2. Base Degradation:

Spectra of base degradation is shown in figure 7 and table 10 shows % degradation in basic condition:

Figure. 7 Spectra of base hydrolysis

Table 10. Base degradation condition

Condition	Time	Absorbance	Conc. obtained (µg/ml)	% Potency	% Degradation
Control	0 hr	0.608	10	100	-
0.1N NaOH	30 mins	0.614	9.32	93.2	6.75

The degradation in basic condition was found to be 6.75 %.

3. Neutral Degradation:

Spectra of neutral degradation is shown in figure 8 and table 11 shows % degradation in neutral condition:

Figure. 8 Spectra of neutral hydrolysis

Table 11. Neutral degradation condition

Condition	Time	Absorbance	Conc. Obtained (µg/ml)	% Potency	% Degradation
Control	0hr	0.608	10	100	-
H ₂ O	30 mins	0.556	8.40	84.0	15.94

The degradation in neutral condition was found to be 15.94 %.

4. Oxidative Degradation:

Spectra of oxidative degradation is shown in figure 9 and table 12 shows % degradation in oxidative condition:

Figure. 9 Spectra of oxidative degradation

Table 12. Oxidative degradation condition

Condition	Time	Absorbance	Conc. obtained (µg/ml)	% Potency	% Degradation
Control	0 hr	0.608	10	100	-
3% H ₂ O ₂	30 mins	0.487	7.33	73.3	26.68

The degradation in oxidative condition was found to be 26.68 %.

5. Photolytic Degradation:

Spectra of photolytic degradation is shown in figure 10 and table 13 shows % degradation in photolytic condition:

Figure. 10 Spectra of photolytic degradation

Table 13. Photolytic degradation condition

Condition	Time	Absorbance	Conc. obtained (µg/ml)	% Potency	% Degradation
Control	0hr	0.608	10	100	-
Direct sunlight	30 mins	0.314	4.58	45.8	54.10

The degradation in photolytic condition was found to be 54.10 %.

6. Thermal Degradation:

Spectra of thermal degradation is shown in figure 11 and table 14 shows % degradation in thermal condition:

Figure. 11 Spectra of thermal degradation

Table 14. Thermal degradation condition

Condition	Time	Absorbance	Conc. obtained (µg/ml)	% Potency	% Degradation
Control	0 hr	0.608	10	100	-
Temp- 45-50°C	30 mins	0.500	7.53	75.3	24.63

The degradation in thermal condition was found to be 24.63 %.

Table 15 Summary of Forced degradation study

Condition	Time	Absorbance	Conc. obtained (µg/ml)	% Potency	% Degradation
0.1 N HCl	30 mins	0.478	7.18	71.8	28.10
0.1 N NaOH	30 mins	0.614	9.32	93.2	6.75
H ₂ O	30 mins	0.556	8.40	84.0	15.94
3% H ₂ O ₂	30 mins	0.487	7.33	73.3	26.68
Direct sunlight	30 mins	0.314	4.58	45.8	54.10
Temp- 45-50°C	30 mins	0.500	7.53	75.3	24.63

Topiroxostat showed significant degradation under photolytic, acidic, and oxidative conditions, with moderate degradation Thermal and neutral environments. Basic degradation resulted in minimal degradation, indicating that Topiroxostat is relatively stable in basic condition and unstable in photolytic conditions.

DISCUSSION

The UV spectroscopic method was developed using methanol as solvent, with maximum

absorbance at 275 nm. The calibration curve obtained with good linearity with a correlation coefficient of 0.9977 within the concentration range of 6-14 µg/ml. Validation studies performed in accordance with ICH Q2 (R2) guidelines. The drug showed varying degrees of degradation under different degradation conditions, indicating its susceptibility to stress factors. Significant degradation was observed under photolytic conditions (54.10%), indicating that the drug is highly photosensitive. Considerable degradation

was also observed in acidic (28.10%) and oxidative (26.68%) conditions, suggesting susceptibility to acid hydrolysis and oxidation. Moderate degradation occurred at elevated temperature (24.63%) and in aqueous conditions (15.94%), while the drug showed least degradation in basic condition (6.75%), indicating relative stability in basic media. The study confirms that the developed method is stability indicating and capable of effectively detecting changes in drug concentration under stress conditions. The developed method is simple, rapid, and reliable for routine analysis and stability assessment of Topiroxostat in pharmaceutical dosage forms.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors declare no conflict of interest and express sincere gratitude to ROFEL Shri G. M. Bilakhia college of Pharmacy for providing necessary facilities and support to carry out this work.

REFERENCES

1. Gout- Symptoms, Causes, Diagnosis, Treatment and Prevention, retrieved March 2026, from [https://www.pacehospital.com/Gout;Symptoms, Causes, Diagnosis, Treatment & Prevention](https://www.pacehospital.com/Gout;Symptoms,Causes,Diagnosis,Treatment&Prevention).
2. Pralhad R. Jadhav, Yogesh Sonawane, Impact of Forced Degradation studies on the formulation and stability of Topiroxostat: A Comprehensive Review, *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and application*, 2025, 10(2):85-93.
3. National Center for Biotechnology Information, PubChem Compound Summary for CID 136232987, Topiroxostat-d4, retrieved March 2026, from <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/Topiroxostat-d4>.
4. Sachhidananda Mahapatra, Soumyaranjan Biswal, Tushar Kanta Behera, Santosh Kumar Dash, Ashutosh Padhan, Development and Validation of a UV Spectroscopic Method for Stability Evaluation of Metformin, *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2025, 3(10):3264-3270.
5. Sandesh R. Chavan, Avinash M. Bhagwat, Mahesh Rao, Atul P. Choudhari, Importance of forced degradation study in pharmaceutical industry- A review, *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2019, 8(5):639-653.
6. Chatwal GR, Anand SK, "Instrumental method of chemical analysis", Himalayan Publishing House Mumbai, Fifth Edition, 2002:149-2.184.
7. Beckett AH, Stenlake JB, "Practical Pharmaceutical Chemistry", CBS Publisher and Distributors, Fourth Edition, Part II, 2002:275-299.
8. Pallavi Suthar, Manali Ram, UV Spectrophotometric Method Development and Validation for the Estimation of Topiroxostat in Bulk and Pharmaceutical Dosage Form, *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2023, 10(6):326-330.
9. ICH Harmonised Tripartite Guideline: Validation of Analytical Procedures: Text and Methodology Q2 (R2); International Council for Harmonisation, Geneva, Switzerland, 2005:4-13.
10. ICH Harmonised Tripartite Guideline: Stability testing of New Drug Substances and Products Q1A (R2); International Council for Harmonisation, Geneva, Switzerland, 2003:1-18.
11. ICH Harmonised Tripartite Guideline: Photostability Testing of New Drug Substances and Products Q1B; International

- Council for Harmonisation, Geneva, Switzerland, 1996:1-8.
12. Patel AP, Kadikar HK, Shah RR, Shukla MH “Analytical method development and validation of First order derivative spectroscopic method for simultaneous estimation of Cinnarizine and Dimenhydrinate in combined dosage form” *Pharma Science Monitor An international journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, 2012, 1 (1), 2493-2505.
 13. Joshi K, Shah N, Dumasaya M, Patel A “Development and Validation of Spectrophotometric Method for Estimation of Lurasidone Hydrochloride: A novel antipsychotic drug in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form” *Pharma Science Monitor An international journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, 2012, 3(4), 2643-2653.
 14. Shukla M, Patel A, Patel M, Patel P, Shah R “Development and Validation of First order derivative spectroscopic method for the Estimation of Olopatadine Hydrochloride and Ambroxol Hydrochloride in their synthetic mixture” *Pharm Sci Monitor*, 2015, 6(1), 119-131.
 15. Dr. Alisha Patel, Heli Desai, Ankita Patel, “Derivatization of Neomycin Sulphate and Area Under Curve Method For Estimation of Neomycin Sulphate and Clobetasol Propionate in Cream” *Journal of advanced scientific research*, 2022, 13 (9), 88-93.

HOW TO CITE: Krishna Tande, Gayatri Paliwal, Alisha Patel, Bhavesh Patel, Forced Degradation Studies of Topiroxostat Tablet by UV-Visible Spectroscopy as Per ICH Guidelines, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, Vol 4, Issue 5, 1407-1418, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20068145>

